

Analytical Approaches to Studying Al-Bukhari's Creative Work

Saidnazarova Gulshan Bolta qizi

Lecturer at the Department of Pedagogy, Bukhara State University

Article information:

Manuscript received: 04 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 04 Sep 2024; **Published:** 28 Oct 2024

Abstract: The article provides a brief overview of the life, scientific activities, and works of Imam Ismail al-Bukhari, as well as a study of the activities of Imam Ismail al-Bukhari today, including the essence of the reforms being carried out in our country.

Keywords: Etiquette, hadith, education, cultural heritage, spiritual and educational work, history, tradition, value.

As Uzbekistan begins to construct a legal democratic society, it focuses on the spiritual and moral growth of its citizens, particularly the youth, who are committed to constructing a new society. Organizing the upbringing of a well-rounded individual has consistently been a crucial necessity and primary objective of societal communities.

Developing national spiritual and moral qualities in young individuals is not possible if they lack knowledge about our people's rich cultural and educational heritage, history, traditions, values, customs, holidays, rituals, and their universal importance.

In the world, man and his dignity, the development of society are evaluated by the rich spiritual heritage left by ancestors and are valued as the foundation of the future, including the spiritual heritage of the great Hadith scholar Imam Ismail Al-Bukhari in Europe and many developed Asian countries are widely studied in research centers. A system of projects, museums and virtual museums, collections, conferences, internet pages, and scientific journals has been implemented, based on the study of the scholar's spiritual and educational views.

During his visit to the Samarkand region in 2019, President Sh.Sh.Mirziyoyev emphasized the need to expand the Imam Bukhari memorial complex: "Here is the memory of our great ancestor Imam al-Bukhari.

If we create conditions for the Muslims who come here, they will witness that we are a country with a great history, and we want to convey this history to the people, especially to the youth. And to ourselves, our work gives a sense of honesty, devotion, gratitude" [1]. Indeed, the scientific and religious heritage of our great compatriot Imam al-Bukhari, who made a great contribution to the development of the science of hadith, has an invaluable place in the spiritual and moral life of our people.

The full names of the great scholar Imam Ismail al-Bukhari, the founder of the "Sahih" direction, are Abu Abdullah Muhammad ibn Ismail ibn Ibrahim ibn Mughira ibn Ahnaf Bardizbah Jofi Bukhari. In the science of hadith, he was awarded the honorable titles of "Amir-ul-Muminin", "Imam al-Muhaddisiyn" ("Leader of all muhaddiths").

Imam Bukhari was born in Bukhara on May 13, 810 AD (in some sources on July 20, 810 AD) (13th day of Shawwal in 194 AH) in an educated, noble and righteous family.

Imam Bukhari traveled extensively throughout his life to all Islamic countries, and to some of them several times. In particular, he traveled several times to the cities of Khorasan, Jibal, Iraq, Hijaz, Syria, Egypt, and Baghdad, where he collected hadiths from muhaddiths.

Imam Bukhari was a talented man from his youth, possessing a very strong knowledge and memory, memorizing every hadith he read and telling it to the person asking for it, correcting the mistakes made in the hadiths by his youthful comrades. According to sources, during his stay in Baghdad, he often wrote books in the dark nights by candlelight and moonlight. If he accidentally thought of something at night, he would light a candle and immediately write down the thought, sometimes turning the candle off and on twenty times.[3]

He showed kindness to those in need, was generous, and bestowed a considerable sum of riches inherited from his forefathers. Another outstanding characteristic of Imam al-Bukhari is that he was distant from any displays of extremism.

If we delve deeper into his masterpiece "Sahih al-Bukhari", we will observe that al-Bukhari handled the information in his book meticulously and cautiously. His complete conviction in the authenticity of the hadiths he collected painstakingly and included in his work reaffirms this view.

Speaking about Imam al-Bukhari's work "Sahih", it should also be noted that in the authentic isnads of this book, there are also narrators who do not belong to the Sunnah. Al-Bukhari believed that the great love and aspiration for hadiths and their strict adherence to them deserve all praise.

This issue is extremely important, and some muhaddiths have also expressed their opinions on this matter. For example, Imam Ahmad ibn Hanbal said: "I have not recorded a single hadith that I did not observe," and one of the great muhaddiths of his time, Waki ibn al-Jarrah, said: "If you want to memorize a hadith, first of all, follow it".

Another muhaddith, Ibrahim ibn Ismail, noted: "In memorizing hadiths, we used, first and foremost, the path of its observance", and the scholar al-Suyuti in his work "At-Tadriyb" describes this process as follows. It is necessary to effectively utilize the hadiths we have heard about prayers, morality, virtues, and righteous deeds. This is, firstly, the zakat of this hadith, and secondly, a good factor for memorizing it.

According to sources, Imam al-Bukhari created more than twenty works during his scientific and creative career. These include: "Al-Jami' as-sahih", "Al-Adab al-mufrad", "Kitab al-kuna", "Kitab al-favoid", "Juz' raf al-yaddayn", "At-Tarikh al-kabir", "At-Tarikh al-avsat", "At-Tarikh al-saghir", "Al-Jami' al-kabir", "Khalq af'al al-ibad", "Kitab az-zuafo as-saghir", "Al-Musnad al-kabir".

Currently, many works of the scientist are being published in our country. The works of Imam Bukhari "al-Jame' as-sahih" and "al-Abad al-mufrad" are also published in thousands of copies several times. Thanks to independence, Bukhari's immortal heritage has returned to his homeland.

Based on the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Celebration of the 1225 th Anniversary of Imam al-Bukhari's Birth According to the Hijri-Qamar Calendar" (April 29, 1997), significant work has been done to study and popularize the scientific legacy of Bukhari, and to perpetuate his memory. On October 23, 1998, an anniversary celebration was held in Samarkand. A huge memorial complex was opened in the village of Khartang in the Chelak district, where the scholar lived forever.

The purpose of this resolution is to deeply study and widely promote the rich heritage of our great compatriot, the Sultan of Hadith science Imam Bukhari, his invaluable contribution to the development of world civilization and science, to educate the younger generation in the spirit of interethnic and interreligious tolerance, mutual respect and strengthening peaceful life, as well as to strengthen spiritual and educational dialogue and cooperation at the international level.

The activities and creative legacy of Imam Ismail al-Bukhari are studied by many of our scholars, and significant work is also being carried out in this direction, including U. Uvatov, who studied the life paths, inner and scientific worlds of the three great muhaddiths (Imam al-Bukhari, Muslim ibn al-Hajjoj, Abu Isa at-Tirmidhi), their human qualities, their contributions to the development of science, the interaction of these hadith scholars, and their scientific and spiritual heritage [5].

To sum up, it can be stated that after becoming familiar with the extensive spiritual legacy of Imam Ismail al-Bukhari, specifically his book "Al adab-al mufrad," it is evident that the text serves as a foundation for spiritual growth and ethics integrity in individuals.

According to these concepts, the essence of examining the spiritual heritage of Imam Ismail al-Bukhari among college students can be described as follows: an individual ideal, self-awareness is a societal requirement, addressing this issue contributes to achieving an important objective like the efficient application of local and global principles, the cultivation of a well-rounded individual. The educational process reflects the spiritual heritage of Imam Ismail al-Bukhari, emphasizing principles such as continuity in upbringing and education, integration with practical experience, consistency, awareness, and active engagement. These principles align with holistic educational practices and the systematic organization of education based on scientific principles. Using the perspectives of the renowned muhaddith on spiritual and moral education facilitates the enhancement of students' spiritual and moral upbringing.

References

1. Visit of Imam Bukhari during the working visit of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Sh. Mirziyoyev to the Samarkand region on August 24, 2022 <https://president.uz/ru/lists/view/5457>
2. Uvatov U. The Sultan of Hadith Science. Literature and Art of Uzbekistan. 1993. October 29. No. 43-44
3. Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf "Treasure of Etiquette"
4. Uvatov U. The Role of the Scholars of Movarounnahr and Khorasan in the Development of Modern Science. - Тошкент, 2020.
5. Juraev B. T. Questions of Moral and Cultural Education in the Samanid Era (on the example of the works of al-Bukhari and al-Farabi) // Modern Society: Current Problems and Prospects for Development in the Socio-Cultural Space. - 2020. - Б. 66-71.
6. Zhuraev B. In the East the emergence and development of pedagogical activity // Current problems of social and humanitarian sciences / Current problems of social and humanitarian sciences / Current problems of humanities and social sciences. - 2022. - Т. 3. - No. S/2. - С. 343-350.
7. Saidnazarova G. B. Skills of Pedagogical Influence // Bulletin of the Master's Degree. - 2019. - No. 4-3 (91). - С. 80-81.
8. Khodjaev B., Juraev B., Amonov M. Forming the spirituality of students and youth through pilgrimage tourism // E3S Web of Conferences. - EDP Scie
9. Samieva Sh. Kh. Important Directions of Innovative Preparation of Youth for Spiritual and Educational Activities // Quality of Life of the Population of Industrial Territories in the "Society 5.0" Strategy. - 2022. - Б. 153-165.